

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF INCOME DISTRIBUTION AMONG THE POPULATION

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Abstract

The article analyzes population income classification and grouping. Also, population incomes are revealed from the coefficients of stratification, that is, funds, deciles, quantiles and stratification. The Djini index and the criterion for assessing the level of inequality in income distribution have been determined.

Annotatsiya

Maqolada aholi daromadlar tabaqalanishi, guruhlanishi tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, aholi daromatlari tabaqalanish koefitsentlaridan, ya'ni fondlar, detsil, kvantil va stratifikatsiya ochib berilgan. Djini indeksi va daromadlar taqsimlanishidagi tengsizlik darajasini baholash mezonini aniqlangan.

Аннотация

В статье анализируется классификация и группировка населения по доходам. Также доходы населения выявляются из коэффициентов стратификации, то есть фондов, децилей, квантилей и стратификации. Определен индекс Джини и критерий оценки уровня неравенства в распределении доходов.

Keywords: income stratification, coefficient, funds, decile, quantile, stratification, economic cooperation, methodology, Djini index, level of inequality and other criteria.

Kalit so'zlar: daromad tabaqalanishi, koefitsent, fondlar, detsil, kvantil, stratifikatsiya, iqtisodiy hamkorlik, metodika, Djini indeksi, tengsizlik darajasi va boshqa mezonini.

Ключевые слова: стратификация по доходам, коэффициент, фонды, дециль, квантиль, стратификация, экономическое сотрудничество, методология, индекс Джини, уровень неравенства и другие критерии.

Introduction. In the context of building a New Uzbekistan, priority is being given to assessing factors that influence poverty reduction, increasing household incomes, ensuring economic competition, accelerating a full transition to market relations, and enhancing the competitiveness of the national economy. Among the key objectives is achieving sustained and inclusive economic growth to reduce poverty by half, while increasing GDP per capita by 1.6 times within the next five years and exceeding \$4,000 in per capita income by 2030, thus positioning Uzbekistan among "upper-middle-income" countries [1, p. 74]. In this regard, aligning income distribution with household living standards and synchronizing economic growth with household incomes and expenditures is a strategic approach.

A significant widening of income inequality can pose threats to both political and economic stability within a country. Consequently, many developed nations are compelled to reduce income disparities among different social groups continually. Income inequality, referring to the differences in income levels per capita or per employed individual, is termed income stratification.

Literature Review. Income distribution and living standards have been widely studied in economic literature by many scholars. For instance, V.N. Salin and E.P. Shpakovskaya from CIS countries highlight that "living standards represent a complex and multifaceted category, reflecting the aggregate of real socio-economic conditions that define social progress" [8, p. 399]. X.D. Khujakulov analyzed income inequality using the Gini coefficient, which measures the degree of

income inequality on a scale from 0 to 1, with a value closer to 1 indicating greater inequality and concentration of wealth in the hands of certain groups. Conversely, a coefficient closer to 0 suggests more equal income distribution [9, p. 4]. According to N.I. Rustamov, the standard of living reflects the material aspects of people's lives, while the quality of life considers the socio-cultural aspects and overall development [7, pp. 34]. He emphasized the relationship between income and expenditures in determining living standards, arguing that as incomes increase relative to expenditures, living standards improve. Rustamov also identified macroeconomic conditions, rapid economic growth, and structural changes in the economy as key factors in raising living standards.

Methodology. The research methodology involves the systematization of theoretical data from general to specific. The decile index was used as the primary indicator based on grouped income data.

Analysis and Results. The study utilized various stratification coefficients, including:

- **Fund coefficient** – the ratio of average incomes between population groups or their share in total income.

In this approach, the population is divided into ten deciles based on income, with each decile representing 10% of the population. The first decile (D1) consists of the population with the lowest income, while subsequent deciles represent groups with increasing income. The fund coefficient compares the average income of the highest-income decile (D10) to the lowest-income decile (D1). In 2022, the average per capita income in

Uzbekistan's first decile was 244,098 soums, while the tenth decile was 1,496,946 soums, resulting in a ratio of 6.1 (23.7% :3.9% or 1,496,946:244,098). This indicates a significant decrease in the fund coefficient from 21.1 in 2000 to 6.1 in 2022.

- **Decile stratification coefficient** – represents the income difference between the wealthiest 10% and the poorest 10%.

- **Quintile stratification coefficient** – measures the income gap between the wealthiest and poorest 25%.

A similar method is applied to the quintile coefficient, except that the population is divided into five

groups, each representing 20% of the population. In 2022, the average per capita income in the first quintile was 293,622 soums (9.3%), while in the fifth quintile it was 1,194,690 soums (37.8%). The quintile coefficient decreased from 9.9 in 2000 to 4.1 in 2022.

- **Stratification coefficient** – represents the ratio of the poor to the wealth.

The Gini coefficient in Uzbekistan decreased significantly from 0.39 in 2000 to 0.262 in 2022, indicating a noticeable reduction in income inequality. This reduction suggests a more equal distribution of per capita income across the population.

Table 1

Evaluation Criteria for Income Inequality Based on the Gini Index According to the Methodology of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)¹

Ko'rsatkich	Assessing criteria
0.20-0.22	Countries with very low inequality
0.24-0.26	Countries with low inequality
0.29-0.31	Countries with moderate inequality
0.33-0.35	Countries with high inequality

According to the United Nations (UN) classification system, which monitors income inequality through the Gini index, the following thresholds are recommended:

- 0.41–0.42: Critical level of inequality

- 0.35–0.37: Marginal level
- 0.25–0.26: Optimal level

Based on this classification, Uzbekistan's Gini index, at 0.262, falls within the "optimal" range, indicating a relatively balanced income distribution.

Table 2

According to the United Nations' methodology for assessing income inequality based on the Gini index, the inequality levels are categorized as follows:²

Ko'rsatkich	Assessing criteria
0.41-0.42	Critical threshold (high inequality)
0.35-0.37	Marginal level (moderate inequality)
0.25-0.26	Optimal level (low inequality)

In addition to income inequality, there is also a notable disparity in personal consumption, which often exceeds income inequality. The level of consumption inequality can be determined through studies of consumer baskets, focusing on households in specific regions and social groups.

Conclusions and Recommendations. In summary, income stratification among the population has been analyzed using the following approaches:

- a comprehensive study of the components, dynamics, and growth rates of living standards indicators.
- an assessment of the population's provision with material goods and services, which serves as a basis for developing overall indicators of living standards.

However, for this methodology to be effectively applied nationwide, we need more detailed data on household incomes. This includes statistical information on the share of the population in each income category high, middle, and low. Reliable data is essential for accurately assessing income distribution and inequality in the country.

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¹ Author's calculations

² Author's calculations

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